

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GERMPLASM

Some panicle characteristics of rice germplasm from the Northern Province of Sierra Leone

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Characterization of important agronomic traits of locally grown rice germplasm in widely variable ecologies is useful to programs breeding rice for adaptability to diverse environments. The agronomic traits of 150 indigenous lowland rice cultivars collected in the Northern Province of Sierra Leone were evaluated at RRRS.

Variations in panicle length and exertion among the cultivars were low (Table 1). Most cultivars displayed good exertion and low spikelet sterility, and a

Table 1. Variation in panicle length, spikelet sterility, and panicle threshability of indigenous rice cultivars from the Northern Province of Sierra Leone, 1987.

Character	Varietal frequency (no.) on the SES ^a scale of 1-9				
	13579				
Panicle length	110	—	32	—	8
Panicle threshability	9	12	47	92	—
Panicle exertion	115	—	29	—	6
Spikelet sterility	—	87	61	2	—

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Table 2. Variability in 1,000-grain weight of some indigenous rice cultivars from the Northern Province of Sierra Leone, 1987.

1,000-grain weight range (g)	Cultivars (no.)
17.6-19.5	5
19.6-21.6	10
21.7-23.0	19
23.1-25.0	27
25.1-27.0	17
27.1-29.0	36
29.1-31.0	30
31.1-33.0	0
33.1-37.0	6

few nonshattering types were identified. The 1,000-grain weight varied widely (Table 2). That of most cultivars averaged 25-29 g; 5 had very small grains, and 6 had very large grains.

Indigenous rice cultivars in Northern

Sierra Leone thus display wide variability in agronomic traits. After further evaluation, some of these cultivars could be used in breeding programs for specific traits to suit the needs of local farmers. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Possibility of a ratoon crop from photoperiod-insensitive summer rices in calcareous sodic soils of North Bihar, India

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Of the 5.6 million ha under rice cultivation in Bihar, about 1 million ha are under irrigated summer rice cultivation (Mar-Apr to Jun-Jul). Crop harvest in Jul-Aug normally coincides with the monsoon rains, thus leaving little time for land preparation for the main wet season (WS) rice planting. A ratoon crop in WS would reduce labor

costs and free farmers for other field operations.

We studied the ratooning ability of 24 advanced breeding lines Mar-Oct 1984 in an experiment in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Forty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 12-m² plots at 2-3 seedlings/hill, with plants spaced 20 cm between rows and 15 cm within a row. Fertilizer was 80-18-17 kg NPK/ha. N was in 3 splits: 25% basal, 50% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. The soil was calcareous sandy loam with pH 8.4 and EC 0.495 µm.

At maturity the main crop was ratooned by cutting the stalks 15 cm above ground. Immediately after harvest, 40 kg N/ha was applied. Ratooning ability [(number of

Performance of ratoon selections. Pusa, North Bihar, India, 1984 DS and WS.

Variety or line	Ratooning ability (%)	Growth duration			Grain yield		
		Main crop (d)	Ratoon crop (d)	% of main crop	Main crop (t/ha)	Ratoon crop (t/ha)	% of main crop
CR222 MW 10	85.8	132	57	43	2.7	1.6	59
IET7617	88.8	129	57	44	2.5	1.1	44
Rasi	87.8	128	57	45	2.4	1.4	58
RP1664-4461-693-1333	94.9	142	59	42	2.4	1.7	71
IR19743-25-2-2-3-1	59.4	129	49	38	2.3	1.1	48
RP1158-172-1	94.0	129	59	46	2.3	1.3	57
IET7613	94.5	133	59	45	2.2	0.8	36
CR215-55-44-1	68.8	128	49	38	2.2	1.3	59
IET3279	91.8	130	61	47	2.1	1.4	67
IR5B-36-70-1	74.3	133	57	43	2.1	1.1	52